

LDA Model with 3 topics

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LDA Model with 3 topics
alphaSum = 114.68991949088144
beta = 0.5182035057708865
Topic 0 tokens=1084.0000      document_entropy=6.1669      word-
length=4.0000 coherence=-21.4049 uniform_dist=1.3888
      corpus_dist=1.9019      eff_num_words=913.7294 token-doc-diff=0.0000
      rank_1_docs=0.1675      allocation_ratio=0.0000
      allocation_count=0.0000      exclusivity=0.5687
      krn word-length=3.0000 coherence=0.0000 uniform_dist=0.0098
      corpus_dist=0.0081 token-doc-diff=0.0000 exclusivity=0.8341
      Fore word-length=4.0000 coherence=-2.1655 uniform_dist=0.0098
      corpus_dist=-0.0026 token-doc-diff=0.0000 exclusivity=0.1569
      ngopi word-length=5.0000 coherence=-2.1655 uniform_dist=0.0098
      corpus_dist=0.0020 token-doc-diff=0.0000 exclusivity=0.4169
      jgn word-length=3.0000 coherence=-2.1655 uniform_dist=0.0066
      corpus_dist=0.0034 token-doc-diff=0.0000 exclusivity=0.5898
      medan word-length=5.0000 coherence=-2.1655 uniform_dist=0.0066
      corpus_dist=0.0067 token-doc-diff=0.0000 exclusivity=0.8459
Topic 1 tokens=1152.0000      document_entropy=6.1849      word-
length=4.6000 coherence=-21.6550 uniform_dist=1.3501
      corpus_dist=1.8435      eff_num_words=935.8984 token-doc-diff=0.0000
      rank_1_docs=0.1419      allocation_ratio=0.0000
      allocation_count=0.0000      exclusivity=0.5988
      Very word-length=4.0000 coherence=0.0000 uniform_dist=0.0090
      corpus_dist=0.0074 token-doc-diff=0.0000 exclusivity=0.8293
      App word-length=3.0000 coherence=-2.1655 uniform_dist=0.0090
      corpus_dist=0.0050 token-doc-diff=0.0000 exclusivity=0.6677
      terima word-length=6.0000 coherence=-2.1655
      uniform_dist=0.0090 corpus_dist=0.0044 token-doc-diff=0.0000
      exclusivity=0.6194
      minum word-length=5.0000 coherence=-2.1655 uniform_dist=0.0090
      corpus_dist=0.0028 token-doc-diff=0.0000 exclusivity=0.4943
      cepat word-length=5.0000 coherence=-2.1655 uniform_dist=0.0090
      corpus_dist=0.0013 token-doc-diff=0.0000 exclusivity=0.3836
Topic 2 tokens=9958.0000      document_entropy=6.9773      word-
length=4.6000 coherence=-17.6959 uniform_dist=1.6331
      corpus_dist=0.1395      eff_num_words=223.4762 token-doc-diff=0.0007
      rank_1_docs=0.9368      allocation_ratio=1.0000
      allocation_count=1.0000      exclusivity=0.9612
      nya word-length=3.0000 coherence=0.0000 uniform_dist=0.1503
      corpus_dist=0.0063 token-doc-diff=0.0004 exclusivity=0.9874
      aplikasi word-length=8.0000 coherence=-1.7314
      uniform_dist=0.0917 corpus_dist=0.0041 token-doc-diff=0.0000
      exclusivity=0.9637
      kopi word-length=4.0000 coherence=-1.7341 uniform_dist=0.0799
      corpus_dist=0.0037 token-doc-diff=0.0000 exclusivity=0.9596
      fore word-length=4.0000 coherence=-1.7029 uniform_dist=0.0773
      corpus_dist=0.0034 token-doc-diff=0.0000 exclusivity=0.9213
      enak word-length=4.0000 coherence=-2.5093 uniform_dist=0.0607
      corpus_dist=0.0030 token-doc-diff=0.0003 exclusivity=0.9741

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topic	cohere...	rank_1...	word-l...	exclusi...	docum...	eff_nu...	tokens	unifor...	corpus...	token-...	allocati...
Topic_0	-21.405	0.167	4	0.569	6.167	913.729	1084	1.389	1.902	0	0
Topic_1	-21.655	0.142	4.600	0.599	6.185	935.898	1152	1.350	1.844	0	0
Topic_2	-17.696	0.937	4.600	0.961	6.977	223.476	9958	1.633	0.140	0.001	1

LDA Model with 4 topics

LDA Model with 4 topics

alphaSum = 102.56110112906327

beta = 0.45657101812330486

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Topic 0 tokens=894.0000 document_entropy=6.0716      word-length=6.4000
      coherence=-21.2593      uniform_dist=1.5749      corpus_dist=2.0548
      eff_num_words=764.0880 token-doc-diff=0.0000 rank_1_docs=0.1520
      allocation_ratio=0.0000      allocation_count=0.0000
      exclusivity=0.6027
jgn  word-length=3.0000      coherence=0.0000      uniform_dist=0.0128
      corpus_dist=0.0076      token-doc-diff=0.0000 exclusivity=0.6464
medan word-length=5.0000      coherence=-2.2784      uniform_dist=0.0086
      corpus_dist=0.0088      token-doc-diff=0.0000 exclusivity=0.7703
orderan word-length=7.0000      coherence=-2.2784
      uniform_dist=0.0086      corpus_dist=0.0044      token-doc-diff=0.0000
      exclusivity=0.4841
tambahkan word-length=9.0000      coherence=-2.2784
      uniform_dist=0.0086      corpus_dist=0.0044      token-doc-diff=0.0000
      exclusivity=0.4841
karyawan word-length=8.0000      coherence=-2.2784
      uniform_dist=0.0086      corpus_dist=0.0078      token-doc-diff=0.0000
      exclusivity=0.6286
Topic 1 tokens=864.0000 document_entropy=6.0200      word-length=6.6000
      coherence=-21.2593      uniform_dist=1.5936      corpus_dist=2.1261
      eff_num_words=752.5161 token-doc-diff=0.0000 rank_1_docs=0.1327
      allocation_ratio=0.0000      allocation_count=0.0000
      exclusivity=0.5964
Point word-length=5.0000      coherence=0.0000      uniform_dist=0.0134
      corpus_dist=0.0123      token-doc-diff=0.0000 exclusivity=0.8146
terjangkau word-length=10.0000      coherence=-2.2784
      uniform_dist=0.0090      corpus_dist=0.0092      token-doc-diff=0.0000
      exclusivity=0.7732
terima word-length=6.0000      coherence=-2.2784
      uniform_dist=0.0090      corpus_dist=0.0044      token-doc-diff=0.0000
      exclusivity=0.5271
birthday word-length=8.0000      coherence=-2.2784
      uniform_dist=0.0090      corpus_dist=0.0082      token-doc-diff=0.0000
      exclusivity=0.7350
Fore word-length=4.0000      coherence=-2.2784      uniform_dist=0.0090
      corpus_dist=-0.0026      token-doc-diff=0.0000 exclusivity=0.1321
Topic 2 tokens=862.0000 document_entropy=5.9716      word-length=7.2000
      coherence=-19.5036      uniform_dist=1.6282      corpus_dist=2.0965
      eff_num_words=714.4654 token-doc-diff=0.0034 rank_1_docs=0.1156
      allocation_ratio=0.0000      allocation_count=0.0000
      exclusivity=0.6772
lingkungan word-length=10.0000      coherence=0.0000
      uniform_dist=0.0134      corpus_dist=0.0113      token-doc-diff=0.0007
      exclusivity=0.7817
minum word-length=5.0000      coherence=-2.0243      uniform_dist=0.0134
      corpus_dist=0.0051      token-doc-diff=0.0005 exclusivity=0.4982
ketagihan word-length=9.0000      coherence=-2.2784
      uniform_dist=0.0090      corpus_dist=0.0082      token-doc-diff=0.0004
      exclusivity=0.6320
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donlot      word-length=6.0000      coherence=-2.2784
           uniform_dist=0.0090      corpus_dist=0.0092      token-doc-diff=0.0015
           exclusivity=0.7733
review      word-length=6.0000      coherence=-2.2784
           uniform_dist=0.0090      corpus_dist=0.0074      token-doc-diff=0.0004
           exclusivity=0.7007
Topic 3 tokens=9574.0000      document_entropy=6.9806      word-
length=4.6000      coherence=-17.7067      uniform_dist=1.7385
           corpus_dist=0.1675      eff_num_words=207.7446      token-doc-diff=0.0007
           rank_1_docs=0.9346      allocation_ratio=1.0000
           allocation_count=1.0000      exclusivity=0.9465
nya        word-length=3.0000      coherence=0.0000      uniform_dist=0.1576
           corpus_dist=0.0079      token-doc-diff=0.0004      exclusivity=0.9815
aplikasi   word-length=8.0000      coherence=-1.7326
           uniform_dist=0.0963      corpus_dist=0.0052      token-doc-diff=0.0000
           exclusivity=0.9536
kopi       word-length=4.0000      coherence=-1.7357      uniform_dist=0.0839
           corpus_dist=0.0046      token-doc-diff=0.0000      exclusivity=0.9484
fore       word-length=4.0000      coherence=-1.7044      uniform_dist=0.0806
           corpus_dist=0.0041      token-doc-diff=0.0000      exclusivity=0.8868
enak       word-length=4.0000      coherence=-2.5132      uniform_dist=0.0638
           corpus_dist=0.0038      token-doc-diff=0.0003      exclusivity=0.9621

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topic	cohere...	rank_1...	word-l...	exclusi...	docum...	eff_nu...	tokens	unifor...	corpus...	token-...	allocati...
Topic_0	-21.259	0.152	6.400	0.603	6.072	764.088	894	1.575	2.055	0	0
Topic_1	-21.259	0.133	6.600	0.596	6.020	752.516	864	1.594	2.126	0	0
Topic_2	-19.504	0.116	7.200	0.677	5.972	714.465	862	1.628	2.096	0.003	0
Topic_3	-17.707	0.935	4.600	0.946	6.981	207.745	9574	1.739	0.167	0.001	1

LDA Model with 5 topics

LDA Model with 5 topics

alphaSum = 87.91783102940249

beta = 0.39672036632666197

```
Topic 0 tokens=771.0000 document_entropy=5.9170      word-length=4.8000
      coherence=-20.1002      uniform_dist=1.7233      corpus_dist=2.2612
      eff_num_words=653.9505 token-doc-diff=0.0148 rank_1_docs=0.1453
      allocation_ratio=0.0000      allocation_count=0.0000
      exclusivity=0.6576
mas   word-length=3.0000      coherence=0.0000      uniform_dist=0.0156
      corpus_dist=0.0143      token-doc-diff=0.0002 exclusivity=0.7711
karna word-length=5.0000      coherence=-2.1473      uniform_dist=0.0156
      corpus_dist=0.0132      token-doc-diff=0.0012 exclusivity=0.6533
Point word-length=5.0000      coherence=-2.4054      uniform_dist=0.0105
      corpus_dist=0.0096      token-doc-diff=0.0009 exclusivity=0.5928
download word-length=8.0000      coherence=-2.4054
      uniform_dist=0.0105      corpus_dist=0.0107      token-doc-diff=0.0115
      exclusivity=0.7224
jgn   word-length=3.0000      coherence=-2.4054      uniform_dist=0.0105
      corpus_dist=0.0061      token-doc-diff=0.0009 exclusivity=0.5484
Topic 1 tokens=709.0000 document_entropy=5.8690      word-length=5.4000
      coherence=-15.6138      uniform_dist=1.7931      corpus_dist=2.3033
      eff_num_words=619.8286 token-doc-diff=0.0200 rank_1_docs=0.1561
      allocation_ratio=0.0000      allocation_count=0.0000
      exclusivity=0.4862
liat  word-length=4.0000      coherence=0.0000      uniform_dist=0.0118
      corpus_dist=0.0079      token-doc-diff=0.0166 exclusivity=0.5967
Fore  word-length=4.0000      coherence=-1.2587      uniform_dist=0.0118
      corpus_dist=-0.0024      token-doc-diff=0.0011 exclusivity=0.1357
enaaaakk word-length=9.0000      coherence=-2.1473
      uniform_dist=0.0067      corpus_dist=0.0080      token-doc-diff=0.0008
      exclusivity=0.6555
berat word-length=5.0000      coherence=-2.1473      uniform_dist=0.0067
      corpus_dist=0.0061      token-doc-diff=0.0008 exclusivity=0.4226
cinta word-length=5.0000      coherence=-2.1473      uniform_dist=0.0067
      corpus_dist=0.0069      token-doc-diff=0.0008 exclusivity=0.6203
Topic 2 tokens=9283.0000 document_entropy=6.9738      word-
length=4.6000 coherence=-17.7421      uniform_dist=1.8402
      corpus_dist=0.1950      eff_num_words=195.4482 token-doc-diff=0.0007
      rank_1_docs=0.9447      allocation_ratio=1.0000
      allocation_count=1.0000      exclusivity=0.9319
nya   word-length=3.0000      coherence=0.0000      uniform_dist=0.1636
      corpus_dist=0.0092      token-doc-diff=0.0004 exclusivity=0.9763
aplikasi word-length=8.0000      coherence=-1.7338
      uniform_dist=0.1000      corpus_dist=0.0060      token-doc-diff=0.0000
      exclusivity=0.9443
kopi  word-length=4.0000      coherence=-1.7373      uniform_dist=0.0854
      corpus_dist=0.0050      token-doc-diff=0.0000 exclusivity=0.8735
fore  word-length=4.0000      coherence=-1.6866      uniform_dist=0.0848
      corpus_dist=0.0051      token-doc-diff=0.0000 exclusivity=0.9136
enak  word-length=4.0000      coherence=-2.5170      uniform_dist=0.0663
      corpus_dist=0.0044      token-doc-diff=0.0003 exclusivity=0.9516
Topic 3 tokens=692.0000 document_entropy=5.9491      word-length=5.2000
      coherence=-17.2445      uniform_dist=1.8269      corpus_dist=2.3896
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    eff_num_words=586.8431 token-doc-diff=0.0083 rank_1_docs=0.0861
    allocation_ratio=0.0000 allocation_count=0.0000
    exclusivity=0.6791
disuruh word-length=7.0000 coherence=0.0000
    uniform_dist=0.0241 corpus_dist=0.0165 token-doc-diff=0.0005
    exclusivity=0.7228
kurir word-length=5.0000 coherence=-2.6103 uniform_dist=0.0180
    corpus_dist=0.0153 token-doc-diff=0.0069 exclusivity=0.7517
berbulan word-length=8.0000 coherence=-1.7986
    uniform_dist=0.0122 corpus_dist=0.0124 token-doc-diff=0.0003
    exclusivity=0.7315
ice word-length=3.0000 coherence=-2.6103 uniform_dist=0.0122
    corpus_dist=0.0102 token-doc-diff=0.0003 exclusivity=0.5841
lwt word-length=3.0000 coherence=-2.6103 uniform_dist=0.0122
    corpus_dist=0.0112 token-doc-diff=0.0003 exclusivity=0.6055
Topic 4 tokens=739.0000 document_entropy=5.9506 word-length=4.6000
    coherence=-19.8395 uniform_dist=1.7717 corpus_dist=2.2559
    eff_num_words=625.5682 token-doc-diff=0.0154 rank_1_docs=0.0605
    allocation_ratio=0.0000 allocation_count=0.0000
    exclusivity=0.4944
error word-length=4.0000 coherence=0.0000 uniform_dist=0.0165
    corpus_dist=0.0070 token-doc-diff=0.0006 exclusivity=0.5101
titik word-length=5.0000 coherence=-2.4054 uniform_dist=0.0112
    corpus_dist=0.0093 token-doc-diff=0.0135 exclusivity=0.5748
offline word-length=7.0000 coherence=-2.4054
    uniform_dist=0.0112 corpus_dist=0.0079 token-doc-diff=0.0004
    exclusivity=0.6155
ter word-length=3.0000 coherence=-2.4054 uniform_dist=0.0112
    corpus_dist=0.0102 token-doc-diff=0.0004 exclusivity=0.6948
kopi word-length=4.0000 coherence=-2.4054 uniform_dist=0.0112
    corpus_dist=-0.0054 token-doc-diff=0.0004 exclusivity=0.0770

```

topic	cohere...	rank_1...	word-l...	exclusi...	docum...	eff_nu...	tokens	unifor...	corpus...	token-...	allocati...
Topic_0	-20.100	0.145	4.800	0.658	5.917	653.950	771	1.723	2.261	0.015	0
Topic_1	-15.614	0.156	5.400	0.486	5.869	619.829	709	1.793	2.303	0.020	0
Topic_2	-17.742	0.945	4.600	0.932	6.974	195.448	9283	1.840	0.195	0.001	1
Topic_3	-17.245	0.086	5.200	0.679	5.949	586.843	692	1.827	2.390	0.008	0
Topic_4	-19.839	0.060	4.600	0.494	5.951	625.568	739	1.772	2.256	0.015	0

LDA Model with 6 topics

LDA Model with 6 topics

alphaSum = 71.11970482687698

beta = 0.36835738564362913

```
Topic 0 tokens=9067.0000      document_entropy=6.9709      word-
length=4.6000  coherence=-17.7678      uniform_dist=1.9052
      corpus_dist=0.2131      eff_num_words=186.8909 token-doc-diff=0.0007
      rank_1_docs=0.9870      allocation_ratio=1.0000
      allocation_count=1.0000      exclusivity=0.9262
  nya  word-length=3.0000      coherence=0.0000      uniform_dist=0.1683
      corpus_dist=0.0102      token-doc-diff=0.0004      exclusivity=0.9707
  aplikasi  word-length=8.0000      coherence=-1.7344
      uniform_dist=0.1035      corpus_dist=0.0068      token-doc-diff=0.0000
      exclusivity=0.9569
  kopi  word-length=4.0000      coherence=-1.7381      uniform_dist=0.0879
      corpus_dist=0.0055      token-doc-diff=0.0000      exclusivity=0.8600
  fore  word-length=4.0000      coherence=-1.7067      uniform_dist=0.0873
      corpus_dist=0.0057      token-doc-diff=0.0000      exclusivity=0.9026
  enak  word-length=4.0000      coherence=-2.5188      uniform_dist=0.0682
      corpus_dist=0.0049      token-doc-diff=0.0003      exclusivity=0.9406
Topic 1 tokens=617.0000 document_entropy=5.7978      word-length=5.8000
      coherence=-20.7224      uniform_dist=1.9506      corpus_dist=2.4111
      eff_num_words=525.0883 token-doc-diff=0.0031      rank_1_docs=0.0804
      allocation_ratio=0.0000      allocation_count=0.0000
      exclusivity=0.5188
  auto  word-length=4.0000      coherence=0.0000      uniform_dist=0.0143
      corpus_dist=0.0120      token-doc-diff=0.0025      exclusivity=0.6361
  mantul  word-length=6.0000      coherence=-1.8609
      uniform_dist=0.0143      corpus_dist=0.0145      token-doc-diff=0.0002
      exclusivity=0.6866
  cepat  word-length=5.0000      coherence=-2.2131      uniform_dist=0.0143
      corpus_dist=0.0035      token-doc-diff=0.0002      exclusivity=0.3381
  pdhl  word-length=4.0000      coherence=-2.2131      uniform_dist=0.0143
      corpus_dist=0.0078      token-doc-diff=0.0002      exclusivity=0.4511
  terjangkau  word-length=10.0000      coherence=-2.2131
      uniform_dist=0.0082      corpus_dist=0.0084      token-doc-diff=0.0001
      exclusivity=0.4823
Topic 2 tokens=608.0000 document_entropy=5.7579      word-length=3.8000
      coherence=-18.5280      uniform_dist=1.9419      corpus_dist=2.4247
      eff_num_words=532.6571 token-doc-diff=0.0210      rank_1_docs=0.0620
      allocation_ratio=0.0000      allocation_count=0.0000
      exclusivity=0.5176
  pke  word-length=3.0000      coherence=0.0000      uniform_dist=0.0145
      corpus_dist=0.0134      token-doc-diff=0.0128      exclusivity=0.5713
  non  word-length=3.0000      coherence=-1.3123      uniform_dist=0.0145
      corpus_dist=0.0134      token-doc-diff=0.0018      exclusivity=0.6616
  chat  word-length=4.0000      coherence=-2.2131      uniform_dist=0.0145
      corpus_dist=0.0106      token-doc-diff=0.0018      exclusivity=0.5938
  bagus  word-length=5.0000      coherence=-2.2131      uniform_dist=0.0145
      corpus_dist=-0.0020      token-doc-diff=0.0018      exclusivity=0.1535
  Mksh  word-length=4.0000      coherence=-2.2131      uniform_dist=0.0084
      corpus_dist=0.0099      token-doc-diff=0.0029      exclusivity=0.6076
Topic 3 tokens=653.0000 document_entropy=5.8927      word-length=4.0000
      coherence=-22.9112      uniform_dist=1.8883      corpus_dist=2.4231
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    eff_num_words=553.0597 token-doc-diff=0.0017 rank_1_docs=0.0816
    allocation_ratio=0.0000 allocation_count=0.0000
    exclusivity=0.6290
  butuh word-length=5.0000 coherence=0.0000 uniform_dist=0.0194
    corpus_dist=0.0179 token-doc-diff=0.0014 exclusivity=0.7355
  App word-length=3.0000 coherence=-2.2131 uniform_dist=0.0194
    corpus_dist=0.0123 token-doc-diff=0.0001 exclusivity=0.5494
  ice word-length=3.0000 coherence=-2.4731 uniform_dist=0.0132
    corpus_dist=0.0111 token-doc-diff=0.0001 exclusivity=0.5468
  Murah word-length=5.0000 coherence=-2.4731 uniform_dist=0.0132
    corpus_dist=0.0134 token-doc-diff=0.0001 exclusivity=0.6819
  Very word-length=4.0000 coherence=-2.4731 uniform_dist=0.0132
    corpus_dist=0.0111 token-doc-diff=0.0001 exclusivity=0.6313
Topic 4 tokens=637.0000 document_entropy=5.8943 word-length=5.0000
    coherence=-18.0199 uniform_dist=1.8838 corpus_dist=2.4285
    eff_num_words=561.2296 token-doc-diff=0.0314 rank_1_docs=0.0837
    allocation_ratio=0.0000 allocation_count=0.0000
    exclusivity=0.6285
  kurir word-length=5.0000 coherence=0.0000 uniform_dist=0.0200
    corpus_dist=0.0171 token-doc-diff=0.0029 exclusivity=0.6295
  APLIKASI word-length=8.0000 coherence=-1.8609
    uniform_dist=0.0200 corpus_dist=0.0160 token-doc-diff=0.0189
    exclusivity=0.6915
  maret word-length=5.0000 coherence=-1.8609 uniform_dist=0.0137
    corpus_dist=0.0139 token-doc-diff=0.0032 exclusivity=0.6840
  Best word-length=4.0000 coherence=-2.2131 uniform_dist=0.0137
    corpus_dist=0.0093 token-doc-diff=0.0032 exclusivity=0.5702
  blm word-length=3.0000 coherence=-2.2131 uniform_dist=0.0137
    corpus_dist=0.0125 token-doc-diff=0.0032 exclusivity=0.5674
Topic 5 tokens=612.0000 document_entropy=5.7474 word-length=5.6000
    coherence=-19.9181 uniform_dist=1.9316 corpus_dist=2.4550
    eff_num_words=539.6888 token-doc-diff=0.0108 rank_1_docs=0.0537
    allocation_ratio=0.0000 allocation_count=0.0000
    exclusivity=0.5909
  karna word-length=5.0000 coherence=0.0000 uniform_dist=0.0144
    corpus_dist=0.0122 token-doc-diff=0.0009 exclusivity=0.5537
  hangus word-length=6.0000 coherence=-2.2131
    uniform_dist=0.0144 corpus_dist=0.0105 token-doc-diff=0.0009
    exclusivity=0.5933
  offline word-length=7.0000 coherence=-2.2131
    uniform_dist=0.0144 corpus_dist=0.0105 token-doc-diff=0.0009
    exclusivity=0.5933
  ide word-length=3.0000 coherence=-2.2131 uniform_dist=0.0083
    corpus_dist=0.0098 token-doc-diff=0.0041 exclusivity=0.6071
  diambas word-length=7.0000 coherence=-2.2131
    uniform_dist=0.0083 corpus_dist=0.0098 token-doc-diff=0.0041
    exclusivity=0.6071

```

topic	cohere...	rank_1...	word-l...	exclusi...	docum...	eff_nu...	tokens	unifor...	corpus...	token-...	allocati...
Topic_0	-17.768	0.987	4.600	0.926	6.971	186.891	9067	1.905	0.213	0.001	1
Topic_1	-20.722	0.080	5.800	0.519	5.798	525.088	617	1.951	2.411	0.003	0
Topic_2	-18.528	0.062	3.800	0.518	5.758	532.657	608	1.942	2.425	0.021	0
Topic_3	-22.911	0.082	4	0.629	5.893	553.060	653	1.888	2.423	0.002	0
Topic_4	-18.020	0.084	5	0.629	5.894	561.230	637	1.884	2.429	0.031	0
Topic_5	-19.918	0.054	5.600	0.591	5.747	539.689	612	1.932	2.455	0.011	0

LDA Model with 7 topics

LDA Model with 7 topics

alphaSum = 76.91375152289883

beta = 0.34296502412606916

```
Topic 0 tokens=502.0000 document_entropy=5.6721      word-length=4.2000
      coherence=-20.0339      uniform_dist=2.1133      corpus_dist=2.6344
      eff_num_words=451.6201 token-doc-diff=0.0235 rank_1_docs=0.1534
      allocation_ratio=0.0000      allocation_count=0.0000
      exclusivity=0.5263
  jgn  word-length=3.0000      coherence=0.0000      uniform_dist=0.0188
      corpus_dist=0.0119      token-doc-diff=0.0047 exclusivity=0.4706
  tambahkan word-length=9.0000      coherence=-2.2770
      uniform_dist=0.0188      corpus_dist=0.0113      token-doc-diff=0.0047
      exclusivity=0.4590
  BNI  word-length=3.0000      coherence=-2.2770      uniform_dist=0.0188
      corpus_dist=0.0173      token-doc-diff=0.0107 exclusivity=0.5511
  ide  word-length=3.0000      coherence=-2.2770      uniform_dist=0.0109
      corpus_dist=0.0127      token-doc-diff=0.0017 exclusivity=0.5754
  shg  word-length=3.0000      coherence=-2.2770      uniform_dist=0.0109
      corpus_dist=0.0127      token-doc-diff=0.0017 exclusivity=0.5754
Topic 1 tokens=575.0000 document_entropy=5.7093      word-length=4.2000
      coherence=-21.7408      uniform_dist=2.0127      corpus_dist=2.4910
      eff_num_words=491.2704 token-doc-diff=0.0045 rank_1_docs=0.1335
      allocation_ratio=0.0000      allocation_count=0.0000
      exclusivity=0.5052
  Fore word-length=4.0000      coherence=0.0000      uniform_dist=0.0229
      corpus_dist=-0.0004      token-doc-diff=0.0006 exclusivity=0.1892
  Point word-length=5.0000      coherence=-2.5387      uniform_dist=0.0157
      corpus_dist=0.0144      token-doc-diff=0.0004 exclusivity=0.5402
  email word-length=5.0000      coherence=-2.5387      uniform_dist=0.0157
      corpus_dist=0.0133      token-doc-diff=0.0015 exclusivity=0.6050
  cita  word-length=4.0000      coherence=-2.5387      uniform_dist=0.0157
      corpus_dist=0.0144      token-doc-diff=0.0004 exclusivity=0.5430
  Cup  word-length=3.0000      coherence=-2.5387      uniform_dist=0.0157
      corpus_dist=0.0159      token-doc-diff=0.0015 exclusivity=0.6486
Topic 2 tokens=571.0000 document_entropy=5.7599      word-length=5.2000
      coherence=-16.4328      uniform_dist=1.9909      corpus_dist=2.5668
      eff_num_words=511.8383 token-doc-diff=0.0248 rank_1_docs=0.1155
      allocation_ratio=0.0000      allocation_count=0.0000
      exclusivity=0.5767
  download word-length=8.0000      coherence=0.0000
      uniform_dist=0.0158      corpus_dist=0.0161      token-doc-diff=0.0141
      exclusivity=0.6491
  size  word-length=4.0000      coherence=-1.3650      uniform_dist=0.0091
      corpus_dist=0.0107      token-doc-diff=0.0027 exclusivity=0.5646
  cinta word-length=5.0000      coherence=-1.9215      uniform_dist=0.0091
      corpus_dist=0.0093      token-doc-diff=0.0027 exclusivity=0.5405
  tbtb  word-length=4.0000      coherence=-1.9215      uniform_dist=0.0091
      corpus_dist=0.0107      token-doc-diff=0.0026 exclusivity=0.5646
  kapok word-length=5.0000      coherence=-1.9215      uniform_dist=0.0091
      corpus_dist=0.0107      token-doc-diff=0.0027 exclusivity=0.5646
Topic 3 tokens=513.0000 document_entropy=5.7222      word-length=6.0000
      coherence=-19.7820      uniform_dist=2.1127      corpus_dist=2.6016
      eff_num_words=448.3288 token-doc-diff=0.0075 rank_1_docs=0.1014
```

allocation_ratio=0.0000 allocation_count=0.0000
exclusivity=0.5591
ketagihan word-length=9.0000 coherence=0.0000
uniform_dist=0.0182 corpus_dist=0.0168 token-doc-diff=0.0007
exclusivity=0.5522
Prini word-length=5.0000 coherence=-2.2770 uniform_dist=0.0182
corpus_dist=0.0168 token-doc-diff=0.0015 exclusivity=0.6351
Kusuma word-length=6.0000 coherence=-2.2770
uniform_dist=0.0182 corpus_dist=0.0155 token-doc-diff=0.0007
exclusivity=0.6142
minum word-length=5.0000 coherence=-2.2770 uniform_dist=0.0182
corpus_dist=0.0077 token-doc-diff=0.0007 exclusivity=0.4202
shake word-length=5.0000 coherence=-2.2770 uniform_dist=0.0106
corpus_dist=0.0124 token-doc-diff=0.0040 exclusivity=0.5737
Topic 4 tokens=556.0000 document_entropy=5.6445 word-length=5.4000
coherence=-16.4328 uniform_dist=2.0057 corpus_dist=2.4603
eff_num_words=505.1242 token-doc-diff=0.0205 rank_1_docs=0.1137
allocation_ratio=0.0000 allocation_count=0.0000
exclusivity=0.5610
pke word-length=3.0000 coherence=0.0000 uniform_dist=0.0164
corpus_dist=0.0151 token-doc-diff=0.0106 exclusivity=0.6288
MENU word-length=4.0000 coherence=-1.3650 uniform_dist=0.0164
corpus_dist=0.0151 token-doc-diff=0.0000 exclusivity=0.5458
packaging word-length=9.0000 coherence=-1.9215
uniform_dist=0.0095 corpus_dist=0.0096 token-doc-diff=0.0042
exclusivity=0.5428
than word-length=4.0000 coherence=-1.9215 uniform_dist=0.0095
corpus_dist=0.0111 token-doc-diff=0.0015 exclusivity=0.5669
sekedar word-length=7.0000 coherence=-1.9215
uniform_dist=0.0095 corpus_dist=0.0086 token-doc-diff=0.0042
exclusivity=0.5206
Topic 5 tokens=8922.0000 document_entropy=6.9859 word-
length=4.6000 coherence=-17.7368 uniform_dist=1.9517
corpus_dist=0.2270 eff_num_words=181.9011 token-doc-diff=0.0007
rank_1_docs=0.9240 allocation_ratio=1.0000
allocation_count=1.0000 exclusivity=0.9117
nya word-length=3.0000 coherence=0.0000 uniform_dist=0.1716
corpus_dist=0.0109 token-doc-diff=0.0004 exclusivity=0.9652
aplikasi word-length=8.0000 coherence=-1.7349
uniform_dist=0.1049 corpus_dist=0.0072 token-doc-diff=0.0000
exclusivity=0.9259
kopi word-length=4.0000 coherence=-1.7387 uniform_dist=0.0903
corpus_dist=0.0061 token-doc-diff=0.0000 exclusivity=0.8701
fore word-length=4.0000 coherence=-1.6876 uniform_dist=0.0885
corpus_dist=0.0060 token-doc-diff=0.0000 exclusivity=0.8677
enak word-length=4.0000 coherence=-2.5204 uniform_dist=0.0696
corpus_dist=0.0052 token-doc-diff=0.0003 exclusivity=0.9298
Topic 6 tokens=555.0000 document_entropy=5.7492 word-length=6.4000
coherence=-13.9547 uniform_dist=2.0432 corpus_dist=2.5306
eff_num_words=483.5557 token-doc-diff=0.0115 rank_1_docs=0.0541
allocation_ratio=0.0000 allocation_count=0.0000
exclusivity=0.5302
diambas word-length=7.0000 coherence=0.0000
uniform_dist=0.0095 corpus_dist=0.0111 token-doc-diff=0.0008
exclusivity=0.5671

Mantaap word-length=7.0000 coherence=-1.3650
 uniform_dist=0.0095 corpus_dist=0.0111 token-doc-diff=0.0084
 exclusivity=0.5671
 Lperlu word-length=6.0000 coherence=-1.9215
 uniform_dist=0.0095 corpus_dist=0.0111 token-doc-diff=0.0008
 exclusivity=0.5671
 berat word-length=5.0000 coherence=-1.9215 uniform_dist=0.0095
 corpus_dist=0.0086 token-doc-diff=0.0008 exclusivity=0.3828
 updated word-length=7.0000 coherence=-1.9215
 uniform_dist=0.0095 corpus_dist=0.0111 token-doc-diff=0.0008
 exclusivity=0.5671

topic	cohere...	rank_1...	word-l...	exclusi...	docum...	eff_nu...	tokens	unifor...	corpus...	token-...	allocati...
Topic_0	-20.034	0.153	4.200	0.526	5.672	451.620	502	2.113	2.634	0.024	0
Topic_1	-21.741	0.134	4.200	0.505	5.709	491.270	575	2.013	2.491	0.005	0
Topic_2	-16.433	0.115	5.200	0.577	5.760	511.838	571	1.991	2.567	0.025	0
Topic_3	-19.782	0.101	6	0.559	5.722	448.329	513	2.113	2.602	0.008	0
Topic_4	-16.433	0.114	5.400	0.561	5.644	505.124	556	2.006	2.460	0.021	0
Topic_5	-17.737	0.924	4.600	0.912	6.986	181.901	8922	1.952	0.227	0.001	1
Topic_6	-13.955	0.054	6.400	0.530	5.749	483.556	555	2.043	2.531	0.011	0

LDA Model with 8 topics

LDA Model with 8 topics

alphaSum = 67.42199732774456

beta = 0.3194800183051631

```
Topic 0 tokens=490.0000 document_entropy=5.6305      word-length=6.4000
      coherence=-20.7717      uniform_dist=2.1552      corpus_dist=2.6948
      eff_num_words=428.7500 token-doc-diff=0.0210  rank_1_docs=0.1596
      allocation_ratio=0.0000      allocation_count=0.0000
      exclusivity=0.5089
App   word-length=3.0000      coherence=0.0000      uniform_dist=0.0282
      corpus_dist=0.0188      token-doc-diff=0.0023 exclusivity=0.5286
download word-length=8.0000      coherence=-2.6042
      uniform_dist=0.0194      corpus_dist=0.0197      token-doc-diff=0.0128
      exclusivity=0.6266
terenak word-length=7.0000      coherence=-2.6042
      uniform_dist=0.0194      corpus_dist=0.0137      token-doc-diff=0.0018
      exclusivity=0.4247
macem word-length=5.0000      coherence=-2.6042      uniform_dist=0.0113
      corpus_dist=0.0131      token-doc-diff=0.0029 exclusivity=0.5397
penasaran word-length=9.0000      coherence=-2.6042
      uniform_dist=0.0113      corpus_dist=0.0103      token-doc-diff=0.0012
      exclusivity=0.4249
Topic 1 tokens=463.0000 document_entropy=5.5489      word-length=5.8000
      coherence=-21.2579      uniform_dist=2.1920      corpus_dist=2.6839
      eff_num_words=419.5088 token-doc-diff=0.0070  rank_1_docs=0.1201
      allocation_ratio=0.0000      allocation_count=0.0000
      exclusivity=0.4846
jgn   word-length=3.0000      coherence=0.0000      uniform_dist=0.0209
      corpus_dist=0.0134      token-doc-diff=0.0003 exclusivity=0.5149
Prini word-length=5.0000      coherence=-2.3409      uniform_dist=0.0122
      corpus_dist=0.0111      token-doc-diff=0.0002 exclusivity=0.5042
nggak word-length=5.0000      coherence=-2.3409      uniform_dist=0.0122
      corpus_dist=0.0081      token-doc-diff=0.0002 exclusivity=0.4395
dimanapun word-length=9.0000      coherence=-2.3409
      uniform_dist=0.0122      corpus_dist=0.0124      token-doc-diff=0.0002
      exclusivity=0.5235
laporan word-length=7.0000      coherence=-2.3409
      uniform_dist=0.0122      corpus_dist=0.0124      token-doc-diff=0.0060
      exclusivity=0.4409
Topic 2 tokens=465.0000 document_entropy=5.6464      word-length=5.8000
      coherence=-23.4498      uniform_dist=2.1890      corpus_dist=2.7677
      eff_num_words=411.8571 token-doc-diff=0.0154  rank_1_docs=0.1429
      allocation_ratio=0.0000      allocation_count=0.0000
      exclusivity=0.6046
plastik word-length=7.0000      coherence=0.0000
      uniform_dist=0.0401      corpus_dist=0.0351      token-doc-diff=0.0007
      exclusivity=0.7323
Point word-length=5.0000      coherence=-2.8124      uniform_dist=0.0208
      corpus_dist=0.0192      token-doc-diff=0.0004 exclusivity=0.6109
liat  word-length=4.0000      coherence=-2.8124      uniform_dist=0.0208
      corpus_dist=0.0147      token-doc-diff=0.0135 exclusivity=0.5432
cash  word-length=4.0000      coherence=-2.8124      uniform_dist=0.0208
      corpus_dist=0.0178      token-doc-diff=0.0004 exclusivity=0.5924
```

enaaaakkk word-length=9.0000 coherence=-2.8124
 uniform_dist=0.0121 corpus_dist=0.0141 token-doc-diff=0.0003
 exclusivity=0.5440

Topic 3 tokens=8795.0000 document_entropy=6.9720 word-
 length=4.6000 coherence=-17.7385 uniform_dist=2.0038
 corpus_dist=0.2384 eff_num_words=175.9612 token-doc-diff=0.0007
 rank_1_docs=0.9455 allocation_ratio=1.0000
 allocation_count=1.0000 exclusivity=0.9121

nya word-length=3.0000 coherence=0.0000 uniform_dist=0.1746
 corpus_dist=0.0116 token-doc-diff=0.0004 exclusivity=0.9599

aplikasi word-length=8.0000 coherence=-1.7354
 uniform_dist=0.1068 corpus_dist=0.0076 token-doc-diff=0.0000
 exclusivity=0.9170

kopi word-length=4.0000 coherence=-1.7393 uniform_dist=0.0931
 corpus_dist=0.0068 token-doc-diff=0.0000 exclusivity=0.9084

fore word-length=4.0000 coherence=-1.7079 uniform_dist=0.0901
 corpus_dist=0.0064 token-doc-diff=0.0000 exclusivity=0.8555

enak word-length=4.0000 coherence=-2.5220 uniform_dist=0.0708
 corpus_dist=0.0055 token-doc-diff=0.0003 exclusivity=0.9197

Topic 4 tokens=466.0000 document_entropy=5.5833 word-length=5.4000
 coherence=-24.1035 uniform_dist=2.2011 corpus_dist=2.6679
 eff_num_words=409.7283 token-doc-diff=0.0056 rank_1_docs=0.0823
 allocation_ratio=0.0000 allocation_count=0.0000
 exclusivity=0.4706

minum word-length=5.0000 coherence=0.0000 uniform_dist=0.0301
 corpus_dist=0.0146 token-doc-diff=0.0002 exclusivity=0.4904

non word-length=3.0000 coherence=-2.6042 uniform_dist=0.0207
 corpus_dist=0.0192 token-doc-diff=0.0002 exclusivity=0.6108

bagus word-length=5.0000 coherence=-2.6042 uniform_dist=0.0207
 corpus_dist=-0.0010 token-doc-diff=0.0002 exclusivity=0.1644

abal word-length=4.0000 coherence=-2.6042 uniform_dist=0.0121
 corpus_dist=0.0140 token-doc-diff=0.0001 exclusivity=0.5438

pemerintah word-length=10.0000 coherence=-2.6042
 uniform_dist=0.0121 corpus_dist=0.0140 token-doc-diff=0.0050
 exclusivity=0.5438

Topic 5 tokens=509.0000 document_entropy=5.6857 word-length=6.2000
 coherence=-22.4861 uniform_dist=2.1066 corpus_dist=2.6355
 eff_num_words=453.7320 token-doc-diff=0.0060 rank_1_docs=0.0718
 allocation_ratio=0.0000 allocation_count=0.0000
 exclusivity=0.5419

ice word-length=3.0000 coherence=0.0000 uniform_dist=0.0184
 corpus_dist=0.0157 token-doc-diff=0.0002 exclusivity=0.5101

Saran word-length=5.0000 coherence=-2.3409 uniform_dist=0.0184
 corpus_dist=0.0170 token-doc-diff=0.0002 exclusivity=0.6039

tingkatkan word-length=10.0000 coherence=-2.3409
 uniform_dist=0.0184 corpus_dist=0.0187 token-doc-diff=0.0002
 exclusivity=0.6237

Shake word-length=5.0000 coherence=-2.3409 uniform_dist=0.0107
 corpus_dist=0.0125 token-doc-diff=0.0053 exclusivity=0.5366

berbulan word-length=8.0000 coherence=-2.3409
 uniform_dist=0.0107 corpus_dist=0.0109 token-doc-diff=0.0001
 exclusivity=0.4353

Topic 6 tokens=499.0000 document_entropy=5.7040 word-length=5.4000
 coherence=-18.6958 uniform_dist=2.1075 corpus_dist=2.6773
 eff_num_words=456.8826 token-doc-diff=0.0076 rank_1_docs=0.0630
 allocation_ratio=0.0000 allocation_count=0.0000
 exclusivity=0.4134

```

app    word-length=3.0000    coherence=0.0000    uniform_dist=0.0189
      corpus_dist=0.0033    token-doc-diff=0.0004    exclusivity=0.2579
ojol   word-length=4.0000    coherence=-1.9824    uniform_dist=0.0189
      corpus_dist=0.0150    token-doc-diff=0.0004    exclusivity=0.5696
berat  word-length=5.0000    coherence=-1.9824    uniform_dist=0.0110
      corpus_dist=0.0100    token-doc-diff=0.0028    exclusivity=0.3662
Banyakin    word-length=8.0000    coherence=-1.9824
      uniform_dist=0.0110    corpus_dist=0.0112    token-doc-diff=0.0020
      exclusivity=0.5175
kemasan    word-length=7.0000    coherence=-1.9824
      uniform_dist=0.0110    corpus_dist=0.0091    token-doc-diff=0.0020
      exclusivity=0.3557
Topic 7 tokens=507.0000 document_entropy=5.6330    word-length=5.0000
      coherence=-19.9924    uniform_dist=2.1355    corpus_dist=2.6210
      eff_num_words=437.9029 token-doc-diff=0.0108    rank_1_docs=0.0475
      allocation_ratio=0.0000    allocation_count=0.0000
      exclusivity=0.5204
karna    word-length=5.0000    coherence=0.0000    uniform_dist=0.0185
      corpus_dist=0.0158    token-doc-diff=0.0023    exclusivity=0.4513
lwt     word-length=3.0000    coherence=-2.3409    uniform_dist=0.0185
      corpus_dist=0.0171    token-doc-diff=0.0005    exclusivity=0.5249
offline    word-length=7.0000    coherence=-2.3409
      uniform_dist=0.0185    corpus_dist=0.0138    token-doc-diff=0.0023
      exclusivity=0.5519
ide     word-length=3.0000    coherence=-2.3409    uniform_dist=0.0107
      corpus_dist=0.0125    token-doc-diff=0.0029    exclusivity=0.5369
diambas    word-length=7.0000    coherence=-2.3409
      uniform_dist=0.0107    corpus_dist=0.0125    token-doc-diff=0.0029
      exclusivity=0.5369

```

topic	cohere...	rank_1...	word-l...	exclusi...	docum...	eff_nu...	tokens	unifor...	corpus...	token-...	allocati...
Topic_0	-20.772	0.160	6.400	0.509	5.631	428.750	490	2.155	2.695	0.021	0
Topic_1	-21.258	0.120	5.800	0.485	5.549	419.509	463	2.192	2.684	0.007	0
Topic_2	-23.450	0.143	5.800	0.605	5.646	411.857	465	2.189	2.768	0.015	0
Topic_3	-17.739	0.946	4.600	0.912	6.972	175.961	8795	2.004	0.238	0.001	1
Topic_4	-24.104	0.082	5.400	0.471	5.583	409.728	466	2.201	2.668	0.006	0
Topic_5	-22.486	0.072	6.200	0.542	5.686	453.732	509	2.107	2.635	0.006	0
Topic_6	-18.696	0.063	5.400	0.413	5.704	456.883	499	2.108	2.677	0.008	0
Topic_7	-19.992	0.047	5	0.520	5.633	437.903	507	2.135	2.621	0.011	0